

A Study on Consumer Preference towards Health Drinks

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Abstract

Marketing plays a major role in our daily lives. Each day is filled with consuming products made available by marketers. Marketing is responsible for satisfying customers, which in turn, increases our standard of living and quality of life. Objectives of marketing to analyse the customer preference level of health drinks. To find out which factors has got influence on customer awareness in health drinks. To identify the customer requirements about the health drinks. The sample is selected from large size of population, but the member were selected at random. The study aims to collect primary data from the health drinkers. And the study further analysis, identified and problems of the consumer preference of health drinks and also attempts to find the right solution to serve them better. The marketing intelligent and capable application of modern marketing policies.

Introduction

Marketing plays a major role in our daily lives. Each day is filled with consuming products made available by marketers. Marketing is responsible for satisfying customers, which in turn, increases our standard of living and quality of life. Marketing being with the fundamental idea that most human behavior is a purposeful quest for need satisfaction and this activity is rooted in "exchange" notion. Marketing requires the existence of two or more persons or groups each having certain wants, and also possessing certain products. Each believes that his total satisfaction will be increased if he exchanges some of the products that possessing for some products of the other party. Exchange is, therefore, the process of satisfying human wants via trade.

Objectives of Study

- To analyses the customer preference level of health drinks.
- To find out which factors has got influence on customer awareness in health drinks.
- To identify the customer requirements about the health drinks.
- To final step is to develop a sound business plan to insure the survival of their chosen firm within its competitive environment.
- To offer suitable suggestions based on the result of the study.

Methodology of the Study

Descriptive Research

Descriptive research design is also called explanatory design. This the one that simply describes something such as demographic characteristics of consumers who use the product. The descriptive study is typically concerned with determining frequency with which something occurs or how to variables vary together. This is study guided by an initial hypothesis.

Sample size

In this study sample size 120 respondents is made as based on convenience sampling.

Collection of Date

The both of Primary date & Secondary date have been collected for research work.

Primary date

The primary date are those which are collection for the first time and a fresh and thus happen to be original in character. The source of information that a researcher should tap way with his interest and types sources. The date from field sources may be collected from person who has a fund of knowledge about social conditions by following observation interview questionnaire and other devices.

Secondary data

Secondary data consists of information that already exists somewhere, which has been collection for specific purpose in this study. The secondary data for this study was collected from various books, websites and organization brochures.

Tools used in this Study

- Percentage analysis
- Chi-square test

Percentage analysis

Percentage analysis refers to a special type of ratio. Percentage is used in making comparison between two percentage analyses and two or more series of data.

Chi-square test

This method is used non-parametric test in statistical work it makes no assumption about being sampled. the quantity chi-square describes the magnitude of discrepancy between theories and observation.

Review of Literature

Review of literature is essential for researcher to carry on the investigation successfully the review of literature helps the researcher to have a first hang knowledge about the parallel work done by other.

Aker (1996) has mention that brand of a particular product plays a fundamental function in consumer's perception of a product. It helps the brand constitutes a mechanism of risk reduction hence selection of brand is another major review of constituent of consumer behavior.

Singh (2007) is of view that production oriented market has been shifting towards consumer oriented market; traditional consumption pattern has also been facing large-scale change.

Shophia. R (2009) in her research thesis entitled, a study on consumer' satisfaction towards various brands of malted milk food in gobichettipalayam town" reveals that majority of the samples

respondents prefer to buy health drinks for its reasonable price, quality, quantity, packing, health care, doctor’s advice, content of vitamin and mineral’s. However, different type of malted milk FOOD manufactures have to concentrate on those aspects and work out better strategy to attract more on of consumers for their brands.

Arun. Kumar. S.K.(2010) in his study on “brand preferences” and consumer satisfaction towards health drinks - A study in Coimbatore city concluded that majority of the respondents preferred by the brand of health drinks, followed by boost. The socio-economic factors like age. Gender, marital status, educations, occupation, income, ect.do not influence the satisfaction of the customer.

Sivakumar. p(2012) in his A study on consumer behavior and preference of health drinks in erode town” “concluded that health drinks is the leading brand in the health food drink market in Indian and as the most trusted drink brand” in India enjoys more than half of the health food drink market. With revitalized packaging synergetic with the new brand personality, it is a favorite its both mother, for its nourishments and with the kids for its great taste and variety.

Gender of the Respondents

S.No	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Male	40	33
2.	Female	80	67
	Total	120	100

Interpretation

From the above table 4.1shows, gender of the respondents in that 67% of the respondents are female and the remaining 33% of the respondents are male.

Age Group of the Respondents

S.No.	Age Group	No.of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Below 20 years	40	34
2.	21 years - 30 years	60	50
3.	31 years - 40 years	10	8
4.	Above 40 years	10	8
	Total	120	100

Interpretation

From the above table 4.3 shows age group of the respondents out of 120 respondents, 50% of the respondents are belonging to the age group between 21-30 years, 34% of the respondents are belonging to the age group of below 20 years, 8% of the respondents are belonging to the age group between 31-40 years, and 8% of the respondents belonging to the age group of above 40 years.

Educational Qualification of the Respondents

S.No.	Educational Qualification	No. of the Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Illiterate	29	24
2.	Higher secondary	20	17
3.	Diploma	10	8
4.	Graduate	61	51
	Total	120	100

Interpretation

The table 4.2 indicate that the educational qualification of the respondents, 51% of the respondents are coming under the category of graduate, 24% of the respondents are coming under the illiterate, 17% of the respondents are coming under higher secondary, 8% of the respondents are coming under the diploma.

Suggestions

- The companies should come up with new types of schemes which would attract more numbers of people toward their product.
- The feedback of the retailer should be collected regularly so that companies can come to know that were they are standing.
- I would recommend that the company should strength its distribution channel especially at local retailer, which is the biggest market for health drinks.
- The company should make use of more advertising media like TV, display at various outlets, etc, that are very useful to increase the awareness regarding the product.

Conclusion

- As the customer is considered to be the king of the market, this fact is very much true for the liquid food drink industries.
- From the survey carried out and after data analysis of the information obtain it can be concluded that people are aware of health drink.
- It is also concluded that television has played a vital role in spreading awareness of health drinks.
- All the information gathered during this survey and after analysis it properly one come to only one conclusion that liquid food drink industries has a great scope in future.

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